

Decentring the Study of Migrant
Returns and Return Policies

Post-Return Practices and Experiences of Returnees in Nigeria

WP8 – Country Survey Report

Authors:

**Ngozi L. Uzomah, Lucy Dim, Eberechukwu J. Ezeh, Ignatius A.
Madu, Chukwuedozie K. Ajaero**

University of Nigeria (UNN)

Co-funded by

Deliverable Information

Project acronym	Decentring the Study of Migrant Returns and Readmission Policies in Europe and Beyond
Project no.	101094341
WP	8
Deliverable title	Post-Return Practices and Experiences of Returnees in Nigeria
Deliverable type	R – Document, report
Version	V1
Date	January 2026
Responsible partners	University of Nigeria (UNN)
Authors	Ngozi L. Uzomah, Lucy Dim, Eberechukwu J. Ezeh, Ignatius A. Madu, Chukwuedozie K. Ajaero
Dissemination level	Public

© UNN

This research was conducted under the Horizon Europe project “GAPS: Decentring the Study of Migrant Returns and Readmission Policies in Europe and Beyond” (101094341). The sole responsibility of this publication lies with the author. The European Union is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein. Any enquiries regarding this publication should be sent to the author at ngozilouisuzomah@gmail.com

Cite as:

Uzomah, N.L., Dim, L., Ezeh, E.J., Madu, I.A. and Ajaero, C.K. (2026). “Post-Return Practices and Experiences of Returnees from European Countries in Nigeria”, in *GAPs Working paper 2026/08*. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18284346

Table of Contents

ABOUT THE PROJECT	3
WP8: POST-RETURN PRACTICES AND EXPERIENCES OF RETURNEES IN NIGERIA	3
1. COUNTRY CONTEXT: NIGERIA	4
1.2 <i>Organisational Structure of Return and Reintegration Governance in Nigeria</i>	5
2. METHODOLOGY	7
3. DEMOGRAPHICS	8
4. COUNTRIES THAT RETURNEES HAD ORIGINALLY ASPIRED TO TRAVEL TO	13
5. TYPOLOGY OF RETURN	14
6. DATE AND ROUTE OF RETURN	15
7. AFRICAN COUNTRIES TRAVELLED TO AS AN EMIGRANT	16
7.1 <i>Secondary and Tertiary African Countries Resided</i>	16
7.2 <i>Total Number of Trips to African Countries</i>	17
7.3 <i>History of African Travels by Returnees</i>	17
7.4 <i>Time Spent in African Countries</i>	18
8. EUROPEAN COUNTRIES TRAVELLED TO AS AN EMIGRANT	19
8.1 <i>Primary European Countries Resided</i>	19
8.2 <i>Total Number of Trips to European Countries</i>	19
8.3 <i>History of European Travel by Returnees</i>	20
8.4 <i>Time Spent in European Countries</i>	21
9. NON-AFRICAN AND NON-EUROPEAN COUNTRIES TRAVELLED TO AS AN EMIGRANT	22
10. LIKELIHOOD OF LEGAL AND ILLEGAL RE-IMMIGRATION	22
11. MOTIVATIONS FOR RETURNING TO NIGERIA	22
12. FINANCIAL SUPPORT FOR RETURN TO NIGERIA	23
12.1 <i>Source of Financial Support for Return</i>	23
12.2 <i>Support from Organisations</i>	24
13. DETENTION EXPERIENCES ABROAD	24
14. MEANING IN LIFE	24
15. COPING WITH LIFE’S DIFFICULTIES AND FRIENDSHIPS	25
16. SOCIAL AND CULTURAL CONNECTIONS	25
17. APPLICATION OF SOCIO-CULTURAL SKILLS LEARNT OVERSEAS	25
18. HOPE, RESILIENCE, DEPRESSION AND PARADOXICAL SELF-STIGMA AMONG RETURNEES ..	26
19. DISCUSSION	28
20. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS	30
<i>Reference</i>	31
<i>Appendix</i>	33

About the GAPs project

GAPs is a Horizon Europe Project that focuses on the drivers of return policies and the barriers and enablers to international cooperation on returns. The project aims to address the disparities between the anticipated outcomes of return policies and their actual results by challenging the dominant, one-sided understanding of "return policymaking." Specifically, GAPs:

- Identifies the missing link in the EU's return policy, considering both its internal and external dimensions.
- Explores factors that facilitate or hinder international cooperation.
- Illuminates the returnees' experiences and sheds light on the factors that shape their resilience, aspirations and hope in the face of adversities.

The GAPs project is structured into 11 Work Packages, each designed to critically examine the existing legal, policy, and institutional frameworks governing return and reintegration processes. These Work Packages aim to identify best practices, uncover structural and operational gaps, and strengthen the overall effectiveness of return governance and management by generating evidence on returnees' lived experiences, resilience, and hope in the face of mounting adversities. Using a field survey-based approach, the project generated evidence-based insights to inform more coherent, equitable, and sustainable return policies.

GAPs fieldwork has been conducted in 14 countries: Jordan, Lebanon, Sweden, Nigeria, Germany, Morocco, the Netherlands, Afghanistan, Poland, Georgia, Turkey, Tunisia, Greece and Iraq. This country report has been compiled in the context of the GAPs Work Package Eight (WP8) on 'Post-Return Practices and Experiences of Returnees in Nigeria.

WP8: Post-Return Practices and Experiences of Returnees in Nigeria

The WP8 focuses on the experiences of returnees in four countries: Afghanistan, Iraq, Nigeria, and Tunis – this report focuses on Nigeria. By conducting representative surveys across these contexts, the objective is to gain a deeper understanding of returnees' aspirations, motivations, and challenges during and after their return. To achieve this, the study employed standardised measurement tools, including the Hope Scale, Resilience Scale, Depression Scale, and (Paradoxical Self-Stigma Scale in the case of Nigeria). These tools allow us to assess the psychological well-being of returnees and examine how broader societal (e.g., community support, social inclusion and exclusion) and structural factors (e.g., access to services, legal documentation, employment opportunities) influence their ability to cope with adversity. Ultimately, the aim is to identify patterns of vulnerability and strength among returnees and to provide evidence that can inform policies and interventions aimed at supporting sustainable reintegration.

Map.1: Nigeria¹

1. Country Context: Nigeria

Nigeria's approach to return and reintegration governance is rooted in several international and regional frameworks that define its obligations toward migrants, refugees, and internally displaced persons (IDPs). These include the 1951 Refugee Convention and its 1967 Protocol, the Kampala Convention on IDPs, and the United Nations Guiding Principles on Internal Displacement. Nigeria is also a party to key human rights treaties, such as the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights and the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women (United Nations, 2016; Udu et al., 2023).

At the national level, the National Commission for Refugees, Migrants and Internally Displaced Persons (NCFRMI) serves as the lead coordinating institution for managing displacement, return, and reintegration (Uzomah et al., 2024). Established in 1989 and upgraded in 2002, the NCFRMI works in collaboration with partners including the International Organisation for Migration (IOM), the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR), the European Union, and national NGOs (NCFRMI, 2025). The Commission is under the supervision of the Federal Ministry of Humanitarian Affairs. It operates through zonal offices across the country and collaborates with subnational-level institutions like state ministries, agencies and departments including the State Emergency Management Agencies (SEMAs) whose parent agency is known as The National Emergency Management Agency (NEMA) at the federal level.

Complementing the NCFRMI's coordination role are several specialised agencies. The National Agency for the Prohibition of Trafficking in Persons (NAPTIP) provides shelter,

¹ GIS Laboratory, Department of Geography and Environmental Sustainability, University of Nigeria, Nsukka (2025).

psychosocial support, and legal aid to trafficking survivors among returnees (NAPTIP Act, 2003). The NEMA offers standby support, such as water, food, and ambulances, immediately upon arrival. The Nigerians in Diaspora Commission (NiDCOM) serves as a liaison for Nigerian citizens abroad, promoting investment, skills exchange, and partnerships while protecting their interests and supporting national development (Michael, 2023). Together, these agencies and their state-level partners constitute the core national framework for managing return, reintegration, and resettlement in Nigeria.

Several key policy documents and cooperative frameworks underpin Nigeria's migration governance system. The National Policy on Migration, first adopted in 2015 and revised in 2025, provides a comprehensive framework for managing migration, including voluntary return and reintegration, in line with international human rights standards (IOM, 2015; 2025a). Nigeria also participates in bilateral and multilateral partnerships such as the EU–IOM Joint Initiative for Migrant Protection and Reintegration, which funds Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration (AVRR) programmes (IOM, 2025b). These frameworks aim to ensure coordinated response mechanisms, promote durable solutions, and align national efforts with international best practices.

1.2 Organisational Structure of Return and Reintegration Governance in Nigeria

The institutional framework for managing return and reintegration in Nigeria is organised around a network of interrelated agencies coordinated by the NCFRMI. At the apex, the Federal Ministry of Humanitarian Affairs, Disaster Management and Social Development (FMHADMSD) provides overarching policy direction. Within this structure, the Directorates of Migration Management, Return and Reintegration, Policy and Planning, and Humanitarian Affairs function as key operational units responsible for programme design, implementation, and inter-agency coordination (Figure 1).

Supporting institutions include NEMA, which manages emergency responses and logistics during mass return or crisis situations, and the NAPTIP, which provides specialised protection and rehabilitation services for trafficking survivors among returnees. NiDCOM serves as a liaison between the Nigerian government and its diaspora population, facilitating communication and coordination during evacuation or repatriation operations. At the operational level, these agencies work closely with international and regional partners such as the IOM, UNHCR, EU, and national civil society organisations (CSOs). Together, they implement programmes ranging from AVRR to livelihood support, psychosocial assistance, and policy advisory services.

State and local governments, through the SEMAs and Local Government Councils, play complementary roles in monitoring, community reception, and facilitating reintegration into local economies. However, as in many contexts, coordination remains a challenge due to overlapping mandates and uneven resource distribution.

In practice, this multi-tiered system is designed to ensure that returnees receive immediate humanitarian assistance upon arrival, short-term reintegration support, and long-term livelihood stabilisation. While this institutional architecture provides the necessary framework for coordinated migration governance, its effectiveness is in doubt. Despite these frameworks, implementation challenges persist. Poor inter-agency coordination, limited funding, and inadequate community engagement often undermine the effectiveness of return programmes (Uzomah & Madu, 2025).

Figure 1: Organisational Chart of Nigeria’s Return and Reintegration Structure

Source: Authors’ investigation (2025)

2. Methodology

The fieldwork for this study employed a mixed-methods approach that combined quantitative surveys with qualitative interviews and focus group discussions. This design provided a nuanced understanding of post-return experiences, coping strategies, and the realities of reintegration among Nigerian return migrants.

A total of 288 Nigerian returnees were surveyed across Lagos (20 February 2024), Abuja (11 December 2024), Benin (10 February 2025), and Owerri (23 April 2025), representing high- and low-population key urban centres where returnees typically resettle upon return. The survey instrument captured demographic characteristics, migration histories, return and reintegration experiences, economic activities, psychosocial well-being, and access to support mechanisms. The data were analysed using SPSS, with descriptive and inferential statistics employed to identify patterns and relationships among returnees. To complement and enrich the quantitative data, a series of semi-structured interviews was conducted with 21 stakeholders comprising 13 males and 8 females who are directly involved in return and reintegration processes in Nigeria (see Table C in the Appendix). These included representatives from state institutions, international organisations, civil society organisations, community leaders, and return migrants. The state actors include those from the National Commission for Refugees, Migrants and Internally Displaced Persons (NCFRMI), National Agency for the Prohibition of Trafficking in Persons (NAPTIP), Ministry of Health, and Ministry of Education, and international organisations include IOM and International Return and Reintegration Assistance (IRARA). The interviews were designed to buttress and clarify some of the survey findings, especially in instances where returnees sought explanation or elaboration on specific questions.

Despite presenting the project, a number of participants remained hesitant to fill out the surveys or grant interviews. Their reluctance stemmed largely from defensiveness or a lack of trust in the broader context of return and reintegration in Nigeria. Information was closely guarded, and tensions existed both among and within government agencies as well as implementing organisations. To navigate these challenges, the chain-referral, snowball approach was used to reach out to returnees, who in turn referred others within their networks. CSOs like the Civil Society Organisation on Migration and Development (CSOnetMADE) and the Network Against Trafficking, Abuse and Labour (NACTAL) helped refer some returnees for the survey. Additional insights were drawn from notes and presentations of Nigeria's Technical Working Group on Migration (TWG) meetings attended by GAPs researchers, as well as from stakeholder roundtables organised under the GAPs Project in Nigeria. A focus group discussion (FGD) was also held in February 2024 at the Patriotic Citizens Initiative (PCI) premises in Lagos. The FGD lasted approximately 90 minutes and included 10 participants (5 males and 5 females) aged 25-40 years, all of whom had returned to Nigeria within the last 10 years. The session explored gendered dimensions of return and reintegration and aspirations for re-migration. Returnees' paradoxical self-stigma, resilience, depression, and hope were also measured. Three of the scales met the minimum acceptable Cronbach's Alpha (α) value for reliability testing, while one did not: Paradoxical self-stigma = 92.1%; Resilience = 80.5%; Depression = 79%; Hope = 40.1%. Several items from the Hope Scale (C, E, G, and K) were negatively worded and reverse-coded in the analysis, thereby increasing the reliability score to 63%. Similarly, items E and H of the Depression Scale were reverse-coded, raising the reliability value to 84%. Researchers faced challenges in clarifying to respondents that depression should not be conflated with "madness," a misconception rooted in prevailing cultural beliefs. Within the community, depression is rarely acknowledged as a legitimate mental health condition and is instead frequently equated with insanity. This misunderstanding required considerable effort to address during the study. However, no items in any of the scales were modified or omitted.

Additionally, during GAPs results dissemination in Nigeria, participants provided some input, which helped strengthen our analysis. A psychologist and psychiatric doctor gave profound insights into the relationship between forced return and depression, substance use, trauma, and clinical crisis. Secondary data were sourced from peer-reviewed journal articles and online materials focused on return migration, reintegration, and migration governance. As the analysis progressed, additional policy documents, project reports, and official publications were incorporated to triangulate findings and strengthen contextual interpretation. These include UNHCR (2025) and publications from GAPs project.

All research activities were conducted in accordance with established ethical standards for social science research. Informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to their involvement in surveys, interviews, and focus group discussions. Participants were briefed on the study's objectives, their right to withdraw at any time, and the voluntary nature of their participation. Respondents' names and personal identifiers were excluded from all datasets and reporting materials. Data were stored securely and used solely for academic and policy research purposes. Sensitive information, especially regarding detention, trauma, or deportation experiences, was handled with empathy and discretion. Institutional clearance was obtained from the Strategic Contacts, Ethics and Publications of the University of Nigeria, Nsukka through the Population–Environment–Development Research Group (PEDRG), which hosted the Nigerian component of the GAPs Project. Ethical adherence was also aligned with the principles of the Horizon Europe research ethics framework governing the project consortium.

3. Demographics

Of the total 288 Nigerian survey respondents, more were males ($n = 163$) than females ($n = 125$). The mean age of the respondents was 34.6 years ($SD = 8.74$). Regarding current residence, 67 respondents resided in Abuja, 77 in Edo State, 41 in Imo State, and 69 in Lagos State. Regarding marital status, 143 respondents identified as single, while 112 were married. Regarding state of origin, respondents were drawn from across Nigeria's 36 states. The highest number comes from Edo (70), Imo (36) and Delta (23), while the lowest comes from Adamawa, Jigawa, Niger and Zamfara. (See Table 1).

Regarding return destinations, 145 returnees arrived in Lagos, making it the most common destination. Other notable destinations include Abuja ($n = 59$), Edo ($n = 52$), and Kano ($n = 15$), while only three returned to Ogun and one to Oyo (see Table 2). Interestingly, Plateau and Taraba States, each with five respondents originally from them, had no returnees who went back there. Similarly, Kogi and Imo States, with 7 and 36 individuals originally from them, respectively, also recorded no returns. This has important implications for reintegration outcomes. It is important to recall that Nigeria's six geopolitical zones have distinct socioeconomic and cultural contexts that shape how returnees are received and reintegrated into society (Uzomah, 2025). When returnees are settled in locations outside their regions of origin, where they have weaker affective, cultural, and social ties, it becomes significantly more challenging for them to reintegrate successfully.

Table 1: Gender Distribution, State of Origin, and Current Residence of Returnees

Items	Respondents
Gender	
Male	163
Female	125
Origin State	
Abia	9
Adamawa	1
Anambra	8
Bauchi	2
Bayelsa	2
Benue	3
Borno	2
Cross River	1
Delta	23
Ebonyi	4
Edo	70
Ekiti	4
Enugu	9
Imo	36
Jigawa	1
Kaduna	6
Kano	10
Katsina	6
Kogi	7
Kwara	6
Lagos	16
Nasarawa	2
Niger	1
Ogun	22
Ondo	7
Osun	3
Oyo	14
Plateau	5
Rivers	2
Sokoto	2
Taraba	5
Zamfara	1
Current Residence	
Abuja	67
Edo	77
Imo	41
Lagos	69
Nasarawa	7
Niger	5
Ogun	19
Oyo	3
Total	288

Source: Authors' computation (2025)

For the highest level of education attained, 4 respondents reported having no formal education, 143 had senior secondary education, 24 possessed technical education, and 18 obtained a Bachelor's degree or its equivalent. In comparison, 4 respondents had a Master's degree or equivalent qualification (See Table 2), showing that many of the respondents have skills which can benefit them and the destination country if legal pathways are expanded.

Table 2: Demographic Profile and Place of Return of Returnees

Item	Respondents
Age Range	
21 – 30	106
32 – 40	120
41 – 50	43
51 – 58	19
Marital Status	
Single	143
Married	112
Divorced	3
Separated	4
Widowed	8
Single mother	10
Engaged	8
Education Status	
None	4
Primary education	37
Junior secondary	48
Senior secondary	143
Technical	24
Certificate/Diploma	5
Higher Diploma	5
Bachelor's equivalent	18
Master's equivalent	4
Place of Return	
Abuja	59
Benin	52
Kano	15
Lagos	145
Ogun	3
Osun	10
Oyo	1
Port Harcourt	3
Total	288

Source: Authors' computation (2025)

In Table 3, regarding stated employment, most ($n = 169$) reported being employed. Among them, stated professions included self-employed ($n = 102$), service and sales workers ($n = 16$), and craft-related trade workers ($n = 17$). This shows that many prefer to be entrepreneurs rather than learn a skill, while 90 is unemployed, reflecting reintegration difficulties. Furthermore, among the 288 returnees surveyed, 98 persons stated that they were engaged in income-generating activities upon return. Compared with their income before leaving Nigeria, the overwhelming majority (218 individuals) reported a decrease in their current income. Also, regarding general socio-economic status, 129 reported no monthly household income, 16 earned less than ₦21,000 (\$13), while the highest numbers of incomes are between ₦41,000

and ₦60,000 (n = 37) and between ₦21,000 and ₦40,000 (n = 30). Regarding business links in the host country, 37 individuals reported having such connections (Table 3).

Table 3: Employment Status, Income Changes, and Business Linkages

Employment	Respondents
Student/apprentice	29
Self employed	102
Clerical support workers	9
Services and sales workers	16
Skilled agricultural, forestry and fishery workers	4
Craft related trade workers	17
Plant and machine operators and assemblers	4
Elementary occupation	4
Temporary work/contract	2
Unemployed	90
Others	11
Post-return income activities	
Yes	98
No	190
Current vs pre-travel income	
Increased	15
About the same	55
Decreased	218
Income	
₦20,000 (\$13) or less	16
₦21,000 and ₦40,000	30
₦41,000 and ₦60,000	37
₦61,000 and ₦80,000	27
₦81,000 and ₦100,000	19
₦101,000 and ₦120,000	13
₦121,000 and ₦140,000	9
₦141,000 and ₦160,000	1
₦161,000 and ₦180,000	4
₦181,000 and ₦200,000	2
₦201,000 (\$134) and above	1
No income	129
Business link in host country	
No	251
Yes	37
Total	288

Source: Authors' computation (2025).

Table 4 shows that the average household size (i.e., number of total members living under the same roof) was 5.0 ($SD = 3.34$). Of the 288 respondents, 243 stated that they had started a business venture upon returning. However, in terms of level of satisfaction with the performance and profitability of the stated venture, 19 stated that they were very satisfied, and 112 were very dissatisfied. In terms of being able to meet their basic financial needs, only 6 respondents stated “yes, totally”, and 94 stated “not at all”.

Table 4: Household Characteristics, Business Engagement, and Financial Well-being

Item	Respondents
<i>Household</i>	
1	36
2	40
3	12
4	41
5	44
6	43
7	16
8	27
12	8
13	18
15	2
Mean	5
SD	3.4
<i>Started business post-return</i>	
Yes	243
No	45
<i>Business performance satisfaction level</i>	
Very dissatisfied	112
Dissatisfied	38
Neutral	66
Satisfied	18
Very satisfied	19
Did not answer	35
<i>Meet basic financial needs</i>	
Yes totally	6
Somewhat yes	33
A little	67
Not really	88
Not at all	94
Total	288

Source: Authors' computation (2025).

Table 5 reveals that in terms of securing loans or accessing credit for business or personal purposes since returning to Nigeria, only 50 returnees stated “yes”. It further shows that a large proportion of respondents (n = 117) reported renting their homes, 30 owned their homes, 28 were squatting with relatives, and 82 leased their premises. A total of 87 respondents reported having one male child between 6 to 18 years of age while only 53 have a female child of the same age range. A large number of respondents did not answer whether they have a male child (184) or a female child (170), highlighting the cultural notion of not counting the number of children one possesses as the gift of children is divine, and should not be counted.

Table 5: Housing Tenure, Loan Access, and Household Child Demographics

Item	Respondents
<i>Loans</i>	

Yes	50
No	238
Status of house lived	
Rental (monthly)	117
Lease (yearly)	82
Purchased and owned	30
Squatting with friends	23
Squatting with relatives	28
Squatting in an uncompleted building	5
Shelter	3
Male children aged 6 to 18	
None	10
1	87
2	62
3	6
4	19
Did not answer	184
Female children aged 6 to 18	
1	53
2	41
3	10
4	11
5	3
Did not answer	170

Source: Authors' computation (2025).

4. Countries that Returnees had Originally Aspired to Travel to

In response to the question, "Which country was the destination for which you emigrated from Nigeria?", respondents provided a variety of responses. While a large proportion originally aspired to emigrate to Germany ($n = 50$) and other EU countries, smaller proportions had originally aspired to emigrate to the USA ($n = 3$) and Canada ($n = 7$), Tunisia ($n = 4$) and Morocco ($n = 1$), highlighting that the final destination for most of them is Europe. Table 6 provides data for these results.

Table 6: Initial Destination Countries Aspired to Emigrate to

Country	Respondents
Austria	14
Belgium	15

Canada	7
Denmark	11
France	18
Germany	50
Ghana	4
Greece	5
Hungary	8
Ireland	8
Italy	22
Lebanon	2
Libya	13
Luxembourg	2
Mali	2
Malta	4
Morocco	1
Netherlands	24
Niger	1
Norway	6
Oman	6
Poland	2
Portugal	2
Romania	2
Saudi Arabia	3
Spain	17
Sudan	8
Sweden	8
Switzerland	10
Togo	5
Tunisia	4
UK	4
Ukraine	3
USA	3
Total	288

Source: Authors' computation (2025).

5. Typology of Return

For the typology of return, as shown in Figure 2, among the 288 respondents, 125 reported being forced to leave the host country, 79 reported being coerced to return while 84 reported a voluntary return.

Figure 2: Distribution by Type of Return

Source: Authors' computation (2025).

6. Date and Route of Return

Most of the respondents reported returning to Nigeria in 2023 (n = 86), while the least returned in 2015 (n = 1). (See Figure 3).

Figure 3: Date of Return

Source: Authors' computation (2025).

In terms of where they returned from, respondents returned to Nigeria via Libya (n = 85), Sudan (n = 23), and Germany (n = 26), with Libya ranking highest. The high number of returns from Sudan is due to the ongoing war in the country. Table 7 provides a breakdown of the data.

Table 7: Number of returnees by country of return

Country	Respondents
---------	-------------

Austria	4
Belgium	5
Denmark	5
France	10
Germany	26
Ghana	5
Greece	5
Hungary	5
Ireland	4
Italy	15
Lebanon	2
Libya	85
Mali	3
Malta	5
Morocco	6
Netherlands	9
Niger	15
Norway	3
Oman	6
Poland	5
Spain	9
Sudan	23
Sweden	5
Switzerland	6
Togo	5
Tunisia	16
Ukraine	1
Total	288

Source: Authors' computation (2025).

7. African Countries Travelled to as an Emigrant

7.1 Secondary and Tertiary African Countries Resided

Table 8 reveals that of the 288 respondents, apart from the primary country through which they returned, 183 reported spending much time in a secondary African country. Among the secondary African countries in which the respondents had spent the most time in before returning to Nigeria, many reported residing in Libya (n = 87), Tunisia (n = 21), Niger (n = 14), and Sudan (n = 14). A total of 78 also reported spending time in a tertiary country—in these instances, Niger (n = 22), Mauritania (n = 15), Senegal (n = 9), and Tunisia (n = 12). Notably, six of them had stayed in 2 or more countries.

Table 8: Distribution of Returnees by Secondary and Tertiary African Countries of Stay

Country	Respondents
Secondary African country spent much time (n = 183)	
Benin	3
Cote d'Ivoire	3
Egypt	3
Gambia	3
Ghana	6
Libya	87
Mali	5
Mauritania	6
Morocco	10

Niger	14
Senegal	3
Sudan	14
Togo	5
Tunisia	21
<i>Tertiary African country spent time in (n = 78)</i>	
Benin	1
Gambia	3
Ghana	2
Guinea Conakry	2
Libya	5
Mali	8
Mauritania	15
Morocco	5
Niger	22
Senegal	9
Sudan	3
Togo	8
Tunisia	12

Source: Authors' computation (2025).

7.2 Total Number of Trips to African Countries

The total number of trips returnees have made to African countries is 224. Table 6 provides a breakdown of the total number of trips² that the respondents had taken to African countries as emigrants. Note that some respondents reported travelling up to 3 different African countries. In this instance, totals pertain to all primary, secondary, and tertiary countries, where relevant. The most common number of total trips to an African country for an individual respondent is 1 (with 108 occurrences), followed by 2 (with 52 occurrences).

In general, the highest trip count for any single respondent is 3 for two individuals each who returned from Malta and Italy, and one individual each from Greece and Libya, revealing that apart from Nigeria, those returning from Europe and Africa already lived in at least one other African country before crossing to Europe or attempting to do so. The overall mean number of trips is 1.32 with a standard deviation of 0.87.

7.3 History of African Travels by Returnees

As stated, all returnees had returned from abroad within the last 10 years before the interview. However, a broad look at the history of emigration to African countries among the 288 respondents reveals emigration started in 2014. Notably, the mean year of emigration among the 288 returnees was 2017.6. The peak was in 2016, and it slowed from 2019, during the COVID-19 pandemic, until 2023. Figure 4 illustrates the history of emigration to African countries.

Figure 4: Historic Instances of Emigratory Travel for Returnees

² Multiple trips to the same country counted as a multiple. For example, several returnees reported having travelled to Libya and Tunisia thrice.

7.4 Time Spent in African Countries

Figure 5 presents the total number of years that returnees who migrated within Africa reported spent abroad.

Figure 5: Years Spent in a Single African Country for All Returnees

Source: Authors’ computation (2026).

A total of 183 respondents migrated within African countries before returning to Nigeria. The most common period of their emigration was 2.17 years, and the mean number of years was 3.63 (SD = 2.1), reflecting that most respondents migrated for about 2 years, but the average is higher because a significant number stayed longer, showing variability in migration

duration. To note, some persons stayed in another African country for almost a decade prior to returning to Nigeria and others stayed about 5 months.

8. European Countries Travelled to as an Emigrant

8.1 Primary European Countries Resided

A significant proportion of returnees, specifically 122 individuals, were residing in 17 different European countries where they returned from. Germany, with 26 participants, has the highest number of returnees who lived and returned from there to Nigeria, while Ukraine (1) and Norway (3) are among the countries with the fewest returnees. The country of residence and return of these 122 participants is provided in Table 9.

Table 9: Countries in Europe resided

European Country	Respondents
Germany	26
Italy	15
France	10
Netherlands	9
Spain	9
Switzerland	6
Sweden	5
Malta	5
Greece	5
Hungary	5
Denmark	5
Belgium	5
Poland	5
Austria	4
Ireland	4
Norway	3
Ukraine	1
Total	122

Source: Authors' computation (2025).

8.2 Total Number of Trips to European Countries

A large proportion of respondents, specifically 147 individuals, reported having travelled to European countries at least once during their time abroad. Among them, 122 returned directly from Europe, while 25 returned from various African countries and had previously made a total of 35 trips to Europe. Altogether, the 147 respondents recorded 229 visits to 17 different European countries, as provided in Figure 5. Of these, the 122 respondents accounted for 157 trips within Europe, with Germany emerging as the most frequently visited destination, with 46 recorded trips. This includes 26 individuals who were returned directly from Germany and 20 others who had previously transited through or resided in other European and African countries before travelling to Germany. Figure 6 illustrates the total number of trips taken by the 147 respondents.

Figure 6: The Total Number of Trips Made Returnees to European Countries (n = 147)

Source: Authors' computation (2025).

The average number of trips for the 147 individuals was 1.42 ($SD = 0.73$). However, the most common number of trips to Europe was 1, with 108 respondents reporting only 1 trip. Those who returned from Niger, Morocco, and Togo also reported travelling to Europe. This shows that some migrants who returned from African countries had already lived in Europe before returning to Nigeria.

8.3 History of European Travel by Returnees

A broad look at the history of emigration among the 122 respondents who returned directly from Europe reveals that emigration began as early as 2014 to Germany, Italy, Switzerland, Sweden, France, and Hungary. Notably, the mean year of emigration among the 141 who never reached Europe was 2017 ($SD = 2.3$ years). Figure 7 illustrates all historical instances of emigratory travel by the returnees to Europe.

Figure 7: Historic Instances of European Emigratory Travel for Returnees

Source: Authors' computation (2025).

8.4 Time Spent in European Countries

A total of 125 of the participants returned from Europe. The histogram in Figure 8 shows the total number of years they reported spending in European countries. As illustrated, in most instances, returnees had spent 2.17 years in Europe, with an average of 3.88 years ($SD = 1.8$). This implies that most Nigerian migrants to Europe migrated for about 2 years, but the average duration is closer to 4 years because a significant number stayed longer. The spread of 1.8 years shows a moderate range of experiences: Migration to Europe is more consistent than within Africa ($SD = 2.1$ in Section 7.4), with respondents' durations clustering more tightly around the mean (about 4 years). In France, migrants stayed an average of 3.2 years, Germany (2.3 years), and Italy (1.7 years). The duration of stay by migrants in Malta and Ukraine are 6 years and 0.2 years respectively. This reveals that many migrants in Ukraine are either long-term residents of the country or spend several years attempting to obtain a visa to move onward. Conversely, migrants in Malta tend to stay for shorter periods, underscoring Malta's role as a transit country to other EU destinations.

Figure 8: Years Spent in European Countries

Source: Authors' computation (2025).

9. Non-African and Non-European Countries Travelled to as an Emigrant

While no returnees reported travelling to Australia, seven had migrated to Canada and three to the United States. The seven returnees who travelled to Canada departed across four years, 2016, 2019, 2020, and 2022, spending between 1.83 and 4.58 years abroad, with estimated return years ranging from 2017 to 2023. Similarly, the three returnees who travelled to the United States all departed in 2018, spending between 1.42 and 5.25 years abroad, and were estimated to have returned between 2019 and 2023. Some returnees travelled to Asian countries. Four took trips to Oman between 2017 and 2020, with durations ranging from 1.17 years to 5.17 years, and two to Lebanon in 2016 and 2018, spending 3.42 years and 1.42 years abroad, respectively.

10. Likelihood of Legal and Illegal Re-Immigration

Respondents were asked about the likelihood for which they would legally and illegally re-immigrate to another country. With response options ranging from 1 = very unlikely to 5 = very likely. Notably, the mean response was as high as 3.84/5.00 (somewhat likely) for the likelihood of legal reimmigration. It was as low as 2.31/5.00 (somewhat unlikely) for the possibility of illegal reimmigration. While most respondents stated that illegal re-migration is not likely on average, a much stronger desire exists among Nigerian returnees to pursue legal re-migration.

11. Motivations for Returning to Nigeria

Returnees were asked to respond to the relevance of 15 different statements pertaining to their motivations to return to Nigeria. Table 10 provides details as to the relevance of each statement.

Table 10: Motivations for Returning to Nigeria

Reasons	SD	D	N	A	SA	M	SD
Poor security in host country	42	26	29	60	131	3.74	1.47

People of host country were unwelcoming	59	52	47	46	84	3.22	1.50
Kidnapping of/attack on migrants in host country	84	27	20	68	89	3.18	1.65
Poor economic condition in host country	55	67	37	60	69	3.07	1.47
Family reunification in Nigeria	63	83	36	23	83	2.93	1.55
Arbitrary detention in host country	83	65	48	42	50	2.69	1.46
Could not get visa/permanent residency in host country	93	57	42	47	40	2.63	1.56
Unemployment in host country	64	96	56	31	41	2.61	1.33
Nobody to look after our family in host country	103	85	29	39	32	2.35	1.37
I love Nigeria (patriotism)	156	43	17	46	26	2.11	1.43
Natural disaster in host country	144	48	46	28	22	2.08	1.32
Improved security situation in Nigeria	122	84	48	30	4	1.99	1.07
Good treatment of people in Nigeria	149	54	43	36	6	1.94	1.16
Improved economic conditions in Nigeria	138	68	56	13	13	1.94	1.12
Improvement of education in Nigeria	141	89	30	27	1	1.81	0.98

Note: SD = Strongly disagree, D = Disagree, N = Neutral, A = Agree, SA = Strongly agree; *M* = mean response for item; *SD* = standard deviation of the response for the item. Responses are ordered by level of agreement, with the most relevant reason at the top and the least relevant at the bottom.

Source: Authors' computation (2025).

As detailed, the most relevant reason for return was that the returnee "Poor security in host country" ($M = 3.74$, $SD = 1.47$) and that the "People of host country were unwelcoming" ($M = 3.22$, $SD = 1.50$).

12. Financial Support for Return to Nigeria

12.1 Source of Financial Support for Return

Of the 288 respondents, 56 reported receiving no form of assistance from any source as part of a voluntary return programme. However, the remaining 232 reported a total of 464 instances of support from the following organisations: IOM (121 persons), African governments, including Nigerian (22 persons), UNHCR (7 persons), European countries (111 persons), and others like the Red Crescent and unknown organisations (5 persons) (Table 11).

Table 11: Financial Support

Entity	Number of Respondents
UNHCR	7
IOM	121
EU/EEA/EFTA	111
African Government	22

Family and Friends	4
Savings	12
Sold My Properties	6
Others	5
Total	288

Note. Others = Red Crescent and unknown entities.

Source: Authors' computation (2025).

12.2 Support from Organisations

Regarding financial assistance, Table 12 provides a breakdown of organisations, their total expenditure, the number of returnees, and the average support provided to returnees.

Table 12: Financial Assistance as Part of Assisted Voluntary Return (AVR) Programme

Organisation	Total Expenditure (₦)	Number of Returnees (n)	Average Expenditure (₦)	Average Expenditure PP (USD ^a)
IOM	17,455,141	66	264,474	179
Nigeria	400,000	3	133,333	90
UNHCR	1,185,866	5	237,173	160
EU countries	8,044,888	26	309,419	209
Red Cross	350,000	1	350,000	236
*Savings	1,015,000	4	253,750	171

Note. PP = per person; conversion; ^aaccording to currency exchange (<https://wise.com/>) as of 9 April 2025: (₦1 = 0.0006750 USD). Some returnees were paid in USD and Euro resulting in conversion into Naira (1 USD = ₦1,629.33, €1 EUR = ₦1,788). *Not part of AVR. Source: Authors' computation (2025).

Notably, the IOM supported the most returnees, a total 66 persons, and provided an average of 179USD to each of those returnees. EU+ countries also assisted 26 persons, averaging 209 USD, and UNHCR provided assistance to five returnees, averaging 160 USD. Other donations were also received from the Red Cross (one instance, 236 USD), the Nigerian government (three cases, averaging 90 USD), and four people used their savings to return.

13. Detention Experiences Abroad

A substantial proportion of returnees had been detained while abroad. Of the total 288 respondents, 120 had reported spending time in detention. A total of 164 reported not being in detention, and four refused to answer that question. Therefore, over 41% of all returnees had spent some time in detention while being overseas.

In terms of total time spent in detention while abroad, most returnees reported spending less than two weeks ($n = 36$). However, others reported more, such as from two weeks to a month ($n = 30$), more than one month though less than two months ($n = 28$), more than two months though less than six months ($n = 5$), and more than six months ($n = 21$).

Finally, 95 of the 120 returnees who reported being detained stated that the detention ultimately led to their deportation and return to Nigeria.

14. Meaning in Life

Returnees were asked about the degree to which they derived meaning from the following four aspects of life: family, friends, religion, and work/school. Response options for each question were on a zero to 10 scale, with 0 meaning no meaning at all and 10 meaning "to the fullest extent". Table 13 provides the mean results for each aspect of life.

Table 13: Where Returnees Find Meaning in Life

<i>Factor</i>	<i>Mean (SD)</i>
Family	5.66 (3.92)
Religion and Spirituality	4.64 (3.95)
Work/School	3.78 (3.34)
Friends	3.70 (3.44)

Note. *SD* = standard deviation of the mean. *Source:* Authors' computation (2025).

Notably, family, religion, and spirituality featured prominently in contributing to returnees' sense of meaning in their lives.

15. Coping with Life's Difficulties and Friendships

Returnees were asked how much each aspect of their lives helped them cope with life's difficulties. Notably, religion and spirituality also feature strongly in this regard with friends also featuring as less relevant to assisting with life's problems. Table 14 provides a breakdown of the relevance of each facet.

Table 14: Where Returnees Find Support to Cope with Life's Difficulties

<i>Factor</i>	<i>Mean (SD)</i>
Family	5.47 (3.73)
Religion and Spirituality	4.36 (3.91)
Work/School	3.57 (3.37)
Friends	3.36 (3.31)

Note. *SD* = standard deviation of the mean. *Source:* Authors' computation (2025).

Regarding friendships, the average number of close friends reported by returnees was 4.36 (*SD* = 8.13). The minimum reported number of friends was zero ($n = 85$) while the maximum was 70. In the case of hardship of any other matter requiring immediate attention, returnees report that in most cases ($n = 185$), family would be the first point of contact with friends ($n = 37$), relatives ($n = 8$), work colleagues ($n = 1$), neighbours ($n = 16$), children ($n = 10$) (note that 30 persons reported having no potential support person).

16. Social and Cultural Connections

Of the 288 returnees, 78 reported not attending a single social or cultural event. However, the remaining 210 participated in a total of 554 events with the following frequency: funeral (115 instances), marriage (124 cases), social gathering (154 instances), religious gathering (134 instances), a form of social recreation (24 cases), and birthday party (55 cases).

17. Application of Socio-Cultural Skills Learnt Overseas

In response to the following question, "How often do you apply the socio-cultural skills learned in the host country in your daily professional interactions in your home country?", most respondents stated slightly ($n = 93$) and rarely or never ($n = 89$). Similarly, the extent to which the socio-cultural skills that the returnees learnt abroad improved their ability to adapt to different cultural contexts in their own countries was also limited, with most responses as: not at all ($n = 91$) and slightly ($n = 91$). In terms of application of skills acquired abroad that were relevant to the job that active returnees were engaged in, most reported that the skills were not really relevant at all ($n = 119$) or not really relevant ($n = 44$).

18. Hope, Resilience, Depression and Paradoxical Self-Stigma Among Returnees

Returnees reported varying levels of hope, resilience, depression and paradoxical self-stigma³. Figure 9 provides an illustration of the level of hope exhibited by the returnees.

Figure 9: Levels of Hope Exhibited by Returnees

Source: Authors' computation (2025).

Levels of hope reported by returnees ranged between a minimum of 2.33 and a maximum of 5.00 (response options ranged between strongly disagree = 1 and strongly agree = 5). The overall mean level of hope was 3.56/5.00 ($SD = 0.56$). This strong psychological state of high hopes is being dangerously strained by institutional failure, which includes the mass reporting of detention experiences abroad (over 41% detained) and the reliance on informal financing (loans from family) for their return. These lead to external stressors like the trauma of detention and the necessity of informal debt.

Response options for each resilience item ranged between “not true at all” = 1 and “true nearly all of the time” = 5. In terms of resilience, returnees reported an average of 3.69/5.00 ($SD = 0.80$). The lowest level of reported resilience was 2.10/5.00, while the highest reported level of resilience was 5.00. Figure 10 provides a visual for the distribution of responses.

Figure 10: Levels of Resilience Exhibited by Returnees

³ See the 12-item hope scale ($\alpha = 65\%$), 10-item resilience scale ($\alpha = 80.5\%$), and 9-item depression scale ($\alpha = 79\%$) and 23-item paradoxical self-stigma scale ($\alpha = 92.1\%$) are available in the Appendix; note that all items exhibited positive point-biserial correlations—see item-rest statistic, CTT R package (Willse, 2018).

Source: Authors’ computation (2025).

The reported average resilience score of 3.69 (SD ≈ 0.80) is exceptionally high, indicating that the majority of Nigerian returnees possess profound psychological fortitude despite enduring involuntary return, detention, and subsequent economic collapse. The returnees’ high resilience and hope affirm that their aspiration to re-migrate legally remains intact, providing the psychological capital necessary to overcome adversity.

For depression, response options ranged between “never or rarely” = 1 and “always or all the time” = 4. The lowest level of reported depression was 1.00/4.00, while the highest reported level of depression was 3.60/4.00. The mean is 2.41, suggesting that, on average, the returnee population is experiencing depressive symptoms almost as frequently as they are not. Figure 11 provides a visual for the reported level of depression of the returnees.

Figure 11: Levels of Depression Exhibited by Returnees

Source: Authors’ computation (2025).

For Paradoxical self-stigma, response options ranged between “strongly disagree” = 1 and “strongly agree” = 5. The lowest level of reported stigma was 1.00/5.00 while the highest reported level of stigma was 4.58/5.00. Figure 12 provides a visual representation of the reported level of paradoxical self-stigma among returnees. The histogram is positively skewed, with most scores clustered on the lower end (1.0–2.5), indicating that many returnees report low stigma.

Figure 12: Levels of Paradoxical Self-Stigma Exhibited by Returnees

Source: Authors' computation (2025).

19. Discussion

The psychosocial realities of Nigerian returnees are best understood through the interrelated concepts of hope, resilience, stigma, and depression. Hope and resilience are not derived from government institutions, which are widely perceived as corrupt and incapable of supporting reintegration. Returnees believe that even when funds are allocated for their welfare, officials will misappropriate them (Paasche, 2022). Instead, their hope and resilience are anchored in family and religion, the two most trusted sources of meaning and support. These internal assets propel returnees to remain strong despite systemic failures. Yet, when resilience is suppressed by structural barriers such as unemployment and lack of livelihood opportunities (UNDP, 2022), it is often redirected into aspirations for re-migration, as individuals seek to escape precarity and rebuild their lives elsewhere.

Stigma is another defining feature of the returnee experience. Failed migration attracts labelling and disdain from communities, leaving returnees marked by social rejection. Some deny being stigmatised, while others respond with aggression as a coping mechanism. This aggression is a big coming-out to fight discrimination, or what Golay et al. (2021) term 'paradoxical self-stigma'. The denial masks deep-seated shame and prevents open acknowledgement of the trauma of deportation. Depression, meanwhile, is a vague concept among Nigerians who summon resilience through religiosity and family support. No wonder Nigeria is one of the happiest places on earth, and its people are too optimistic (Adewunmi, 2011; Oke, 2024). Even when returnees are depressed, they get resilience from this belief system. The concept of depression is culturally misunderstood; rather than being recognised as a legitimate mental health condition, it is often equated with madness. This

misrepresentation of madness carries severe social consequences. Families, therefore, conceal the suffering of deported loved ones to protect their reputation (Uzomah, 2025), further compounding the silence around stigma and depression. These bottled-up emotions can escalate into clinical crises, leaving returnees vulnerable to severe psychological breakdowns. It can also lead to substance abuse, as noted by participants in our final GAPs research findings dissemination in Nigeria.

Against this backdrop, returnees' critical internal asset is severely strained by systemic failures. The current policy, which sends individuals back to unfamiliar cities and forces them to navigate administrative hurdles, leads to burnout rather than recovery. The return to locations other than their state of origin negates their core coping mechanisms of family and religion, thus elevating psychological exhaustion and an escalation of depression. Any new stressor such as the failure of a business venture, a major family illness, or prolonged unemployment could easily push the mean above 2.50, indicating a population suffering from widespread clinical need. This may result in significant distress becoming a defining mental health crisis for the entire returnee community. Additionally, the pattern of stigma reflects a paradox common in traumatised populations, rather than an absence of shame. It suggests denial or repression as coping mechanisms to manage intense shame or aggression to cope with discrimination of failed migration, as noted by officials of international organisations and government agencies, as well as CSOs. In contrast, the small group with higher scores (4.0–5.0) represents those unable to suppress these feelings, experiencing severe internalised shame, self-blame, and psychological distress tied to their returnee status. These individuals may be the most acutely aware of their internal suffering and, possibly, at higher risk for severe mental health outcomes (like depression, which is often measured alongside stigma).

Despite these challenges, findings confirm that while Nigerian returnees face an overwhelming reality of economic collapse and institutional failure, their capacity for personal and social recovery is anchored in remarkable psychosocial strengths. The mean scores for hope (3.56/5.00) and resilience (3.69/5.00), both well above the midpoint, demonstrate that this population is not psychologically defeated, but instead possesses the inner fortitude necessary to pursue a better future, symbolised by their enduring aspiration for legal re-migration. This profound resilience is not institutional but familial and spiritual, rooted in the highest-rated sources of meaning and support: family and religion. This means that the core infrastructure for successful reintegration already exists within the community, but it remains unsupported by formal governance. The relatively high resilience standard deviation ($SD \approx 0.80$) indicates considerable variability across the population. While many demonstrate profound resilience and hope, rooted in family and religion rather than trust in government institutions, a significant minority struggle to cope, leaving them vulnerable to psychological exhaustion and depression. This uneven distribution means that resilience is not uniformly protective; for some, systemic failures such as unemployment, lack of livelihood, and stigma suppress their coping capacity, potentially pushing them toward maladaptive strategies like denial, aggression, or aspirations for risky re-migration. Thus, the high SD underscores that although the returnees, as a whole, show remarkable strength, hidden subgroups remain at acute risk, highlighting the need for trauma-informed interventions that support the vulnerable while reinforcing the natural psychosocial assets of the majority. The complex issue of stigma further underscores the need for a trauma-informed approach. While most report low stigma, this is often a coping mechanism of denial (positively skewed distribution), masking deep-seated shame from the failed migration journey. A small, severely distressed minority reports high stigma, placing them at acute risk for depression and highlighting the danger of ignoring the underlying emotional trauma caused by involuntary return and detention. The formal governance system, which returns individuals to unfamiliar cities and fails to provide sustainable livelihoods, actively undermines this natural resilience, converting personal strength into a means of merely surviving precarity rather than achieving genuine reintegration.

20. Conclusion and Recommendations

In sum, the experiences of Nigerian returnees reveal a profound tension between systemic failure and individual resilience. While current policies exacerbate psychological exhaustion by severing returnees from their core coping mechanisms of family and religion, the community itself demonstrates remarkable reserves of hope and resilience that could serve as the foundation for reintegration. Yet, without institutional support, these strengths are reduced to survival strategies rather than pathways to recovery. The paradox of stigma, where denial masks deep-seated shame and a distressed minority, bears the full weight of internalised trauma, underscores the urgency of a trauma-informed approach. Sustainable reintegration, therefore, requires governance that recognises and reinforces the psychosocial assets already present among returnees, transforming resilience from a fragile coping mechanism into a genuine engine of recovery and reintegration.

To effectively leverage the high levels of hope and resilience in this population, interventions must pivot from transactional aid to psychosocially-informed, community-driven development. These include the following:

A. Psychosocially-Led Economic Reintegration

- **Harness Family Capital for Business Support:** Move beyond generic micro-credit by using the family network as the primary vehicle for economic reintegration. Micro-loan programmes should be structured around family and communal guarantees rather than individual collateral, recognising that family is the most trusted source of support. This ensures that economic aid reinforces, rather than strains, the primary source of resilience.
- **Skill Transfer through Mentorship:** Instead of relying on foreign skills with limited local applicability, interventions should facilitate mentorship programmes that pair returnees with respected local religious and community leaders or successful self-employed individuals and returnees. This transfers practical, relevant knowledge and simultaneously helps mitigate internalised shame and stigma by connecting the returnee to successful figures, including well-reintegrated returnees within their affective community.

B. Trauma-Informed Stigma and Mental Health Care

- **Normalise the Narrative of Return:** Develop community engagement campaigns (using religious and community platforms, as these are the core sources of meaning) that focus on resilience and recovery rather than “failure.” Interventions should shift the community narrative to view the returnee not as a failure, but as a survivor who demonstrated courage by attempting a difficult journey.
- **Targeted Mental Health Outreach:** Establish flexible, non-stigmatising mental health referral pathways. Given the widespread issue of repression/denial and the small, highly vulnerable group with high stigma/depression, mental health screening and services must be discreetly embedded within existing CSO and religious support structures, where returnees are already comfortable, to reach those at highest risk without triggering further shame.
- **Community Participation in Migration Policy and Mental Health Awareness:** Communities should be actively involved in the migration policy process and provided with the capacity to create awareness. This ensures that members understand that depression is not “madness” but a treatable mental illness, which, if left untreated, can degenerate. Empowering communities in this way strengthens psychosocial resilience and reduces stigma.

C. Strengthening Affective Governance Links

- **Match Returns to Affiliation:** The NCFRMI and partners must incorporate the returnee's state of origin or proven effective connection (family residence) as a primary factor in planning return locations. Ending the practice of dropping individuals in

commercial hubs (Lagos, Abuja, Kano) without their emotional support systems will immediately reduce the financial and social friction that leads to remigration.

- Institutionalise Support for Hope: Reintegration programmes must include dedicated components that translate the returnees' high hope levels into tangible future planning. This involves career counselling and training focused explicitly on legal re-migration pathways and opportunities, channelling their persistent aspiration away from irregular and dangerous journeys.
- Expand Legal Migration Pathways: Results show that many Nigerian returnees will still remigrate irregularly; consequently, the space for safe migration should be broadened so that people do not resort to irregular migration. Such irregular migration contravenes the rules and regulations governing migration and often results in forced return and consequent trauma in Nigeria.

Reference

- Adewunmi, B. (2011, January 4). Nigeria: The happiest place on earth. *The Guardian*. <https://www.theguardian.com/global/2011/jan/04/nigerians-top-optimism-poll>
- Golay, P., Moga, M., Devas, C., Staecheli, M., Poisat, Y., Israel, M., Suter, C., Silva, B., Morandi, S., Ferrari, P., Favrod, J., & Bonsack, C. (2021). Measuring the paradox of self-stigma: psychometric properties of a brief scale. *Ann Gen Psychiatry* 20(5). DOI: 10.1186/s12991-021-00325-7
- IOM. (2015). *National migration policy 2015- Nigeria*. International Organisation for Migration. file:///C:/Users/Dr.%20N.%20L.%20Uzomah/Downloads/national_migration_policy_2015.pdf
- IOM. (2025a, October). *Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration*. IOM. <https://nigeria.iom.int/assisted-voluntary-return-and-reintegration>
- IOM. (2025b, April 30). *Government of Nigeria validates the 2025 National Migration Policy*. IOM, UN Migration. <https://nigeria.iom.int/news/government-nigeria-validates-2025-national-migration-policy>
- Michael, Y. (2023, May 6). Nigerians left in Sudan will be evacuated soon, says NiDCOM. *TheCable*. <https://www.thecable.ng/nigerians-left-in-sudan-will-be-evacuated-soon-says-nidcom/>
- NAPTIP Act (2003). <chrome-extension://efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcglclefindmkaj/https://lawsofnigeria.placng.org/laws/T23.pdf>
- NCFRMI (2025). National Commission for Refugees, Migrants and Internally Displaced. https://ncfrmidps.com.ng/wp/?page_id=45
- Oke, A. (2024, March 20). Nigeria ranks as happiest country in Africa. *Life*. <https://guardian.ng/life/nigeria-ranks-as-happiest-country-in-africa/>
- Paasche, E. (2022). Corruption and return migration. In R. King & K. Kuschminder (Eds.), *Handbook of return migration* (pp. 185–198). Edward Elgar Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.4337/9781800377493.00023>
- Udu, E., Uwadiogwu, A. & Eseni, J. (2023) Evaluating the Enforcement of the Rights of Women under the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women (CEDAW) 1979: The Nigerian Experience. *Beijing Law Review*, 14, 764-782. doi: 10.4236/blr.2023.142041.

- UNDP. (2022). UNDP guidance note: Building resilience through livelihoods and economic recovery. United Nations Development Programme. <https://www.undp.org/publications/building-resilience-through-livelihoods-and-economic-recovery>
- UNHCR. (2025). *Facts and figures*. <https://www.unhcr.org/ng/>
- United Nations (2016, January 11). *Combined seventh and eighth periodic reports submitted by Nigeria under article 18 of the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women*. CEDAW/C/NGA/7-8. <https://docs.un.org/en/CEDAW/C/NGA/7-8#:~:text=2.1%20Previous%20reports%20made%20it,of%20birth%20against%20any%20citizen>.
- Uzomah, N. L. (2025). Regional Disparities in Returnee Support, Stigmatisation and Reintegration in Nigeria. *International Migration*, 63(5), e70103. <https://doi.org/10.1111/imig.70103>
- Uzomah, N. L., & Madu, I. A. (2025). “Reassessing Return Migration Governance: Insights on Nigeria’s Return Migration Infrastructures. WP3 Country Dossier” in *GAPs: Decentring the Study of Migrant Returns and Readmission Policies in Europe and Beyond. Working paper 2025/13*. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15222377
- Uzomah, N. L., Madu, I. A., Ajaero, C. K., & Ezea, E. J. (2024). Navigating the Complexities of Return Migration and Reintegration: Challenges and Opportunities for Nigerian Migrants from North Africa in the Context of EU Policies (v.1). *GAPs: De-centring the Study of Migrant Returns and Readmission Policies in Europe and Beyond*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14238373>

Appendix

The four scales met the minimum acceptable Cronbach's alpha (α) for reliability: Paradoxical Self-stigma = 92.1%; Resilience = 80.5%; Depression = 78.7%; Hope = 63%.

Table A: Paradoxical Self-Stigma and Hope

Item	Item description	r
Paradoxical Self-Stigma: M = 30.31, SD = 8.23		.923
Q1a	People in my condition are less useful to the society	.923
Q1b	The restricted rights of people with my condition is scandalous	.916
Q1c	Because of people's ignorance about my condition, I do not speak to anybody about the problems linked to it	.916
Q1d	I tell myself, "What is the point of struggling to have the same rights?"	.919
Q1e	I am really fed up with preconceived ideas about my condition	.915
Q1f	Because of people's preconceptions, I do not speak to anybody about the problems linked to my condition	.916
Q1g	People with my condition should be banned from certain jobs	.923
Q1h	The public's lack of knowledge about my condition outrages me	.917
Q1i	To stop myself from getting into trouble, I avoid situations where my condition might be revealed	.917
Q1j	Why bother making any effort when I am inferior to others?	.915
Q1k	The lack of accurate information about my condition is scandalous	.913
Q1l	I use strategies to avoid talking about my condition	.917
Q1m	People with my condition should not be allowed to carry out certain activities	.924
Q1n	The stereotypes about my condition make me angry	.915
Q1o	To avoid being discriminated against, I use strategies not to have to talk about my condition	.915
Q1p	People with my condition will never have a happy life	.922
Q1q	The media's lack of knowledge about my condition is appalling	.918
Q1r	To avoid disagreeable remarks, I use strategies not to have to talk about my condition	.915
Q1s	People with my condition should stay among themselves	.922
Q1t	I am angry about the way my condition is caricatured on television	.918
Q1u	To avoid any prejudice, I choose who I talk to about my condition	.915
Q1v	I have come to terms with the idea that I will never be able to have a satisfying social life	.921
Q1w	Certain people's attitudes towards my condition appals me	.915
Q1x	I do not reveal my condition to anybody to avoid being judged	.914
Hope: M = 42.76, SD = 6.68		
Q1a	I can think of many ways to get out of a jam	.597
Q1b	I energetically pursue my goals	.618
Q1c	I feel tired most of the time	.611
Q1d	There are lots of ways around any problem	.597
Q1e	I am easily downed in an argument	.612
Q1f	I can think of many ways to get the things in life that are important to me	.631
Q1g	I worry about my health	.671
Q1h	Even when others get discouraged, I know I can find a way to solve the problem	.552
Q1i	My past experiences have prepared me well for my future	.606
Q1j	I've been pretty successful in life.	.584
Q1k	I usually find myself worrying about something	.588
Q1l	I meet the goals that I set for myself	.569

Table B: Resilience and Depression

Item	Item description	r
Resilience: M = 39.33, SD = 6.17		
Q1a	I am able to adapt when changes occur	.766
Q1b	I can deal with whatever comes my way	.772
Q1c	I try to see the humorous side of things when I am faced with problems	.818
Q1d	Having to cope with stress can make me stronger.	.783
Q1e	I tend to bounce back after illness, injury or other hardships	.785
Q1f	I believe I can achieve my goals, even if there are obstacles	.797
Q1g	Under pressure, I stay focused and think clearly	.789
Q1h	I am not easily discouraged by failure	.798
Q1i	I think of myself as a strong person when dealing with life's challenges and difficulties	.784
Q1j	I am able to handle unpleasant or painful feelings like sadness, fear, and anger	.780
Depression: M = 27.63, SD = 6.51		
Q1a	I was bothered by things that usually don't bother me	.740
Q1b	had trouble keeping my mind on what I was doing	.741
Q1c	I felt depressed	.741
Q1d	I feel that everything I do is an effort to remain alive	.784
Q1e	I am optimistic and hopeful about the future	.816
Q1f	I felt fearful	.731
Q1g	My sleep was restless	.730
Q1h	I was happy	.837
Q1i	I felt lonely	.781
Q1j	I could not "get going."	.741

Note. α = alpha; r = Cronbach alpha value of the scale if item is removed from the scale; Response options for self-stigma were "Strongly disagree" = 1, "Disagree = 2" = , "Neutral" = 3, "Agree" = 4, "Strongly agree" = 5; Response options for hope were "Strongly disagree" = 1, "Disagree = 2" = , "Neutral" = 3, "Agree" = 4, "Strongly agree" = 5; Response options for resilience were "Not true at all" = 1, "Rarely true" = 2, "Sometimes true" = 3, "Often true" = 4, "True nearly all the time" = 5; Response options for depression were Rarely or none of the time" = 1, "Some or a little of the time" = 2, "Occasionally or a moderate amount of time" = 3, "All of the time" = 4.

Table C: Demography of Interviewees

Item	Frequency
Gender	
Male	13
Female	8
Marital Status	
Single	4
Married	12
Widowed	2
Divorced	2
Separated	1
Age Group	
20 -30	3
31 - 40	4
41- 50	9
51 - 60	3
61- above	2
Category	
Returnees	7
Local NGOs	5
Community leaders	2
Government agencies	4
International organisation	2
Location of Interview	
Office place	6
Migrant shelter	7
Open place	4
Home	4
Total	21